

Norbert Tempel: Preservation Challenges of Big Concrete Structures – The Voelklingen and Henrichshuette ironworks as examples

Abstract

Large concrete structures like bunkers and silos for ore or coal are perhaps the most ignored parts of industrial monuments. Older structures have their origin in the 2nd half of the 19th century, but the main part of the surviving reinforced concrete constructions have been built in the first half of the 20th century. Often they are supposed to last without any conservation intervention. But these buildings normally show a bundle of damages, all of these will in the long run cause serious losses of substance, and risks for employees and visitors of a site.

The contribution will provide a short survey of typical structures, the appearance and mechanisms of damages and the influences behind.

Due to their former function these structures often have no roofs and therefore they are collecting and conducting rain to the lowest point: bolts, affiliated with conveyor systems - made from steel and thus being predisposed for corrosion. In this case the well-directed drainage of water turns out to be a good preventive measure.